

**THE MORPHOLOGY, DISTRIBUTION ECOLOGY, CHEMICAL
COMPOSITION AND APPLICATION IN FOLK MEDICINE OF THE FAMILY
REPRESENTATIVES OF FABACEAE, DISTRIBUTED IN THE FARGONA
VALLEY**

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Jumanazar Mamarasulov

*Student of the Department of Botany and biotechnology,
Fergana State University*

Sayramov Fayzullo Baratjon o'g'li

Fergana State University, agrarian joint faculty student

Annotation.

this article provides general information about the family of Dwarves , The family of dwarves found in the Fergana Valley, brief information about alfalfa, sebarga, dwarf, yantok, licorice, achmia, kashgarbeda, bagrak, astragal, legendary, peas, blue peas, beans, peanuts, soybeans.

Keywords.

Cornermates, alfalfa, sebarga, corner, yantok, anise, akmia, kashgarbeda, bagrak, astragal, legendary, peas, blue peas, beans, peanuts, soy.

The Hornbills (Fabaceae-Bobovie) are a family in the magnoliyatoifa section of plants, ancestor of the magnoliaceae, tribe of rañocabii. It consists of more annual or perennial grasses, hemispheres, shrubs or trees. The root of the representatives of the family - the axial Root is systemic. Nodular bacteria at the root live cooperatively. They live on the roots of these plants and absorb free nitrogen in the air. Nodular bacteria enrich the soil with nitrogen compounds, increasing soil yield. The stems are erect, growing, tangled, creeping or lying. In most of them, the leaves are complex or simple, with or without a clover, with a specific structure, with three-pointed, odd or even-patchy, double-patchy complex leaves are found, located in series. Some plants form a stem from their petals or an odd leaflet at the tip of complex leaves with an odd feather. An odd leaflet that dies without developing well can form a spike in place. The flowers are curved, dioecious, chingulate, arranged in a nodule on the Head(Head)cha variety. The inflorescence is made up of 5 inflorescences added up to half. The inflorescence is callous and formed from 5 gultojibargs. The 2 attached gultojibargs located at the base of the

two sides are called the “boatswain”, the one located next to the two - the “wing” (“OAR”), on which the large one is called the “sail” (“flag”). The pollinators are 10, of which the threads of 9 are fused with each other, while the tenth is free, the Seeder is 1. It is often chagged with the help of hashorots. The fruit is legumes, consisting of 1 fruit leaf. Dry or succulent, single or polygonal, open from above in two circles. Distributed in almost all of the globe, the Plant List site contains 24,505 species, grouped into 946 orders, 182 species in Central Asia, 124 endem species, and 57 genera containing 528 species in Uzbekistan.

The family of siblings is separated into 3 younger families:

1. Mimosaceae (Mimosaceae) 2.
2. Caesalpindoches (Caesalpinaceae)
3. 3. Butterflies (Fabaceae or Papilionaceae)

Medicago L. generation includes over 100 species. It has annual and perennial, cultural and wild species. In our country, 36 species of Bede are found, of which 20 species are perennial. The most cultivated and distributed species are: blue alfalfa-*Medicago sativa* L., yellow alfalfa (sickle) - *Medicago falcata* L., hybrid beda-*M. media* L., zangori beda-*M. coerulae* L., khmelsimon beda-*M. lupulina* L. The root is developed as energetic, the arrow root penetrates into the soil to a depth of 8-10 m. In the first year, the roots penetrate to a depth of 2-3 m. At the roots, the tubers are formed B'ladi. Roots are the main component of the supply of humus to the soil in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The STEM is herbivorous, serrated, 50-150 cm tall. stems form 3-4 in the first year, 15-17 in the second year, and 20 or more in the third year. In sparse fields, the number of stems can reach 100. Leaves are three double. The band of the leaflet in the middle is long. The leaves have lateral leaflets. The upper half of the leaves are toothed. In the first year, the leaves make up 50% of the surface mass, and 2-3 years 40%. The inflorescence is a raceme of many flowers. Bisexual, the flower band is short. The inflorescence is light purple or light blue in color. The cockroaches are green, five-pointed. Their father (changdon) 10, their Seeder 1. They are located inside the boat. The crown consists of a sail, wings, a paddle. Alfalfa is an entomophilous plant that is pollinated from the outside using insects. The fruit is a multi-seeded legume, spirally twisted 2.5-5 times. The seed is kidney-shaped, small, with a light yellow tint. Beda is irrigated and planted on lalmikor land in Uzbekistan. It grows well in all provinces, in soils of different types. Bede can be grown on heavy and light, gravelly, loamy, gravelly, saline soils to obtain a high yield. Sebarga (*Trifolium pratensis*) grows on irrigated land, ditches, wet areas in the Fergana Valley. Sebarga is a perennial herb growing to 25-50 cm tall. The STEM is thin, ascending, serrated. The Leaf is complex with three

plates and is arranged in series on the stem with a band. The petals at the bottom are ovoid, with a small tooth-like Edge, the ones on the upper side are oblong, with a flat edge. The flowers are pink or reddish and are clustered differently. The fruit is a single-seeded, ellipsoid or oblong ovoid pod. Blooms in April –September, the fruit ripens in June-October. When the plant blooms, the flower cluster and the leaves at the top of the STEM are collected, and the shade is dried on the ground. The Sebarga plant contains vitamin C, carotene, essential oil, glycosides, Tar, saponins, flavonoids, salistil, kumar acids and other compounds. Abu Ali ibn Sina treated undiluted herbal juices when they were white on wounds and eyes, and used a decoction of the plant's ground top as a urinary Medicine in urinary tract disease.

Lathyrus sativus L. is an annual herb belonging to the cornea. The STEM is 4-pointed, the Leaf is a pair of feathery, complex, the flowers are rusty, pink, red, purple. The pods are oblong and slightly flat, with 4-7 seeds. 12 species that also grow wild are common in Uzbekistan. The corner is mainly a fodder crop, planted to obtain grain, poppies, hay and suppress silage, and graze livestock. Its grains contain a lot of protein compared to peas and apricot peas. The seed contains 24-30% protein, 0.8 – 1.5% oil, 50-55% starch, 3-6% kletchatka, 2.1-4% ash. The corner is a very nutritious feed. A nitrogen-accumulating plant in the soil. It is planted in European Russia, Western Siberia, southern Ukraine, Kazakhstan. 35-50 s of grain per hectare, 100 s provides Cannon (salmon). The yield of Blue Grass is around 300 C.

Alhagi L. is a genus of perennial weeds in the dwarf family. 5 species are known from the steppe, steppe, chala steppes of Central Asia and the Chala steppes of the European part of Russia. In Uzbekistan, the false yantok of Yantak and the Kyrgyz yantak species grow.

1. Alhagi canescenc (Regel) B Keller Shap-grey yantok
2. Alhagikirghisorum Schrenk
3. Alhagi pseudalhagi () (born 1963) is a Danish politician.Bieb) Dasv.ex B. Keller Shap-fake yantok
4. Alhagi persarum Boiss-Persian yantog

Yantok species under natural conditions produce generative organs well, produce flowers and pollinate to produce seeds. The germination of seeds is good in laboratory conditions (when the humidity is 70-90 %, the temperature is 30-35%), and the germination is 40-60%. 40-110 cm tall, erect, sershox, stems strongly developed, reaching to groundwater (10 m or more) . The leaf axils have stiff spines. The leaves are elongated, pubescent, the Leaf band is short, the ketmaket is

located. The flowers are small, red or pink. It blooms in May-September, fertilizing in August – October. Legumes, the fruit of which is up to 10 seeds. The above-ground part of the yantak dries up in winter, new stems grow out of the shoots on the root throat in spring. The seed and root multiply from the bachki. The seed pods germinate very slowly due to their toughness. All types of yantak are good feeders in camelry and sheep farming. Various tinctures are prepared in folk medicine from Guli and root. High-quality Hawthorn, silage and food flour are obtained from yantak. Yantok is a good honey-giving plant. In treeless deserts, Yantok is used as firewood. Grows as a weed on irrigated land, road, ditch, channel banks, abandoned land, cultivated land. Measures of struggle: crop rotation, drive the Earth deeper, harvest iddizpoyas, put rotted manure in the fields, etc.

Syrymia (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*-L.) is a perennial herbaceous plant in the cornflower family (Fabaceae). In his works, Theophrastus named the plant after solodkoviy koren, skifskaya trava, pontiyskaya trava. This plant is called in Russian –solodka golaya, in Uzbek-Shirin, chuchukmia, anise, and in the Autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan-makeup. The distribution area of Shirin is very wide, and the sibik is distributed in the European part of the Union, Crimea, the Caucasus, Siberia, Asia Minor, Iran, Afghanistan, North Africa. On the territory of our republic, shirmiya is considered a typical weaving plant and is found mainly in the lower parts of Syrdarya and Amudarya. Sweetmia is a Polycarp herbaceous plant, the stems are well developed and have a cylindrical structure. The height of the STEM is 150-160cm, and sometimes its height increases by 200cm and even more in weaving conditions. In saline soil conditions, these indicators are recorded around 50-70cm. The leaves have a complex structure. It consists of 4-8 pairs of petals, arranged in series on the stems. The leaf length is 11-18cm, the petals are ovoid, ellipsoid, the circumference is whole, pubescent, the length is 5cm, the width is 2.5 cm. The flowers are white-purple, the pollinators are large, heavy. Being a powerful nectar separator, it attracts bees and other insects. The ground top of the shimmering is used as nutritious feed for animals. The stem contains 11-18% protein, 10-15% proteins, 3.3-9.1% fat and other useful compounds. The underground part of the trunk consists of a brown stem and idlyz stems and is recorded around 180-200cm in length. In roots and rhizomes, the amount of glycyrrizine acid is 3-24%, glucose-8%, sucrose-11%, starch-34%, kletchatka-24%. The amount of extractive substances in water reaches - 43%. From our republic, sweetmia raw materials are exported to developed countries such as the United States, Great Britain, Germany, Japan, Korea. It is worth noting that this plant is not demanding on soil conditions. Groundwater is undoubtedly significant for its

ability to improve the reclamation of land while achieving high economic efficiency by cultivating it in areas left over from the close, re-saline agricultural cycle.

Kashgarbeda is a biennial weed species with arrow roots native to cormorants. Yellow-Chestnut and white-chestnut species are found in Uzbekistan. The stem grows erect, sershox, 50-150 cm tall. The leaves are three-lobed, arranged alternately. The flowers are collected in a yellow, Peaty ball. Fruit 1-2pcs pods. It blooms in June-August in its second year and fruits in July–September. Reproduces from seed. Seeds germinate at a temperature of 4-16°. It is widely distributed in Fergana, Namangan, Samarkand, Kashkadarya regions. Among grain crops, bedapoyas are found in growers, as well as in field edges, ditch collars, roadsides, abandoned lands, sometimes in gardens. Bargak is a genus of monoecious and perennial plants in the legume family, Hemlock crops. More than 130 wild species are known, about 75 species grow abundantly in the European part of Russia, in Central Asia, the Caucasus in forest, steppe, mountain regions. Ordinary or ekma bagrak, loamy bagrak and Zakavkazye bagragi types are planted. Almost all species are good feeders for livestock. The simple Bagram Root is axial, penetrating into the soil to a depth of 3-6 m. The STEM is herbaceous, grows erect, 50-150 CM in height, ovate, hairy, hollow, sparsely branched, 5 – 8 branched. The leaves are complex odd-patchy, with two veined lateral leaves. The Flower Is Pink, collected in a long bulb with many flowers, pollinated from the edge, the fruit is one-seeded pods, round, not chatn. The seed is loamy, light brown. The weight of 1000 taurugs is 12-15 g. Bagrak is a common nutritious plant, 100 kg of hay contains 53.5–54 nutrient units and 11.9–12.6 kg of protein, depending on the species. Bagrak is rich in rosehip, honey can be collected at 120-170 kg/ha. In planted fields, it enriches the soil with nitrogen (accumulates nitrogen per 100-200 kg/ha). Hay can be obtained on irrigated land at 150 c/ha.

Astragalus O is a genus of plants in the daisy family. The Astragal consists of grass, chala Bush and sometimes shrubs. There are 1600 species. The leaves are usually complex, odd-patchy. The flowers are located in a calyx or spike-like inflorescence. Fruit-legumes. 592 species grow in Central Asia and 250 in Uzbekistan. Talaigine (peas, singren) is considered a good forage. From Astragal (*Astargal piletocladus*, *Astragal turcmenorum*), which grows in copetdog and Turkmenistan, a tragacanth glue is obtained, applied in medicine, in the confectionery industry and in techniques, insoluble in water, but only astringent. Some species have the substance glycerizine, flavonoids and microelements in the Earth's crust. The tincture is used in the treatment of hypertension.

Mythopsis ("Thermopsis") is a genus of perennial grasses in the daisy family. It grows mainly in Asia and North America. Most are poisonous. Some species grow among crops. In Central Asia, there are 3 species of this order, the leaves of the species called *Thermopsis dolichocarpa* and *Thermopsis alterniflora*, which are distributed in Uzbekistan, are three-petaled, the STEM is hairy; the flowers are collected in a yellow shingle ball, the cocoon is flattened hairy; the pods are tapered elongated, slightly buckled, hairy. The seeds are brown, sometimes bluish. Blooms in summer. A. some types of sputum are used in medicine as a transducer and respiratory center excitatory drug.

Peas are an annual and perennial herbaceous plant species belonging to the corn family; legume grain crop. Native To Asia. The STEM is herbaceous, grows erect, rough, ribbed, sershox, hairy, 30-70 cm high. The Leaf is complex, patchy. The flower is dioecious, butterfly-shaped, small. The fruit will be legumes, 1-2 grains in legumes, goh 3. Grain color is white, pink, orange, heat-loving and light-loving, spring crop. Resistant to drought and salinity compared to other legumes, the seed germinates at a temperature of 2-5°C, grows slowly at low temperatures. Grass tolerates blackberries until spring-6-8°C. If the humidity exceeds the norm, it gets sick, shona and guli are spilled. Pollinated by itself. The growing season is 70-190 days. The grain contains 19-33% protein, 4-7% oil, 0.2-4.0% ash, 48-61% nitrogen-free extractive, 2-12% klechatka, vitamins and amino acids. On one hectare of land in one season, pea roots accumulate nitrogen in the account of 50-70 kg of pure substance. It is planted in wide rows (45-60 cm between the rows) or in rows in a row (15 cm between the rows), sometimes 5-10 cm deep in a sprinkling method. Most tulips are planted in Uzbekistan. During the flowering period, giving water in low moderation gives a good result, when fully ripe, the flower is shed, the pods are practically not chatnazh, the harvest is harvested in grain combines. Currently, 11 varieties of peas are grown in Uzbekistan.

Pea (*Cicer*) is an annual herbaceous plant species of the corn family, legume grain crop. More than 30, mostly perennial species are found in Eurasia, North and East Africa. A very old annual cultural type (*Cicer arietinum*) is planted in India, Italy, southern Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Greece, Bulgaria, Egypt, Algeria, Turkey and Iran. The root of the cultivated peas is the arrow root (100-150 CM). The STEM is herbaceous, grows erect, rough, ribbed, sershox, hairy, 30-70 cm high. The Leaf is complex, odd pubic. The flower is dioecious, butterfly-shaped, small. The color is white, yellow, yellowish-green, light pink and blue. Fruits-legumes, in the Duchy there will be 1-2 grains, goho-3 grains. The weight of 1000 seeds is 220-300 g, sometimes up to 600 g. The color of the grain is white, pink,

orange. Peas are planted on porous, loamy, lightly saline soils. Black, Ox, Chestnut give a rich harvest on soils. Peas are a heat-loving, light-loving, bakhri crop. Resistant to drought and salinity compared to other legumes, the seed germinates at a temperature of 2-5°, grows slowly at low temperatures. The grass tolerates spring-6° to -8° blackberries. Peas are demanding on heat during flowering and fruiting formation. If the humidity exceeds the norm, it gets sick, shona and guli are spilled. Pollinated by itself. The growing season is 70-190 days. Porridge from pea grain, especially in Uzbek cooking, is prepared for various dishes, a confectionery product, bread is closed from it (YU – 20% is added to wheat flour), surrogate coffee is produced. The grain contains 19-33% protein, 4-7% oil, 0.2-4.0% ash, 48-61% nitrogen-free substances, 2-12% kletchatka, vitamins and amino acids. Peas are considered a good predecessor to wheat and acorns. On one hectare of land in one season, pea roots accumulate nitrogen in the account of 50-70 kg of pure substance. Peas yield 6-8 s/Ha in the lalmi lands of Uzbekistan and 22-32 s/Ha in irrigated lands. In Uzbekistan, varieties of Zimistani, flavor, Uzbekistan32, Yudduz are planted.

Beans (*Phaseolus*) – an annual and perennial plant of the corn family, lianas, a genus of chalky shrubs; a cereal crop with legumes. In the tropics and subtropics, more than 200 species are found, mainly in America. In World Agriculture, the use of beans in the form of ordinary beans (*P. vulgaris*) type (Homeland – central and South America) is the most tapered. Also planted are polygonal beans, lima beans, thin-leaved beans, Asian beans, adzuki beans, rice beans and other species. Fields where beans are planted on Earth 22 mln.ga (1999). It is grown in large areas in India, Brazil, China. In Uzbekistan, ordinary beans have been planted since ancient times. Root-axial Root, well developed, penetrates into the soil to a depth of 1.5-2 m. At the root, the tubers develop. The STEM is herbaceous, branching, some species rot and grow up to 3-4 m. The Leaf is complex, odd, patchy, three-lobed. The Guli are dioecious, arranged one at a time in the leaf axils, or forming a shingle cluster. The fruit is legumes, the color is pale pink or dark brown, Cora. The pods will contain 6-12 seeds. The seed is kidney-shaped, the color is white, yellow, pink and other. 1000 grains 50-370 g. Beans are a heat-loving plant, urugi germinate at least 8-10°. Grass dies at – 0.5, - 1.0°. 15-18° for mowing, the most favorable temperature for flowering is 18-25°, and 20-23° for fruiting. Beans are moist-loving, planted on wetlands in Uzbekistan. Demanding on fertile soil conditions. The growing season is 75-120 days. Porridge is rich in protein, has a high calorie content. Canned food is produced from Whole unripe beans and grains. The grain contains 20-31% protein, 0.7-3.6% oil, 50% starch, 2.3 – 7.1% kletchatka, alkyl acids.

The STEM is a good feed for livestock. Some species are planted as ornamental plants. Enriches the soil with nitrogen. Ground walnut is a heat-loving, moisture-loving, light-loving and short-day plant. Demanding on sand and fertile soils, it does not grow well on saline and waterlogged lands. The seed germinates at 12-15°, the grass dies at -1° Frost. The growing season is 150-170 days. In Uzbekistan, the ground is planted on irrigated land with a yield of 20-40 s/Ha. The fruit contains 48-66% fat, 23-38% protein and up to 22% carbohydrates. Seeds and oil are used in confectionery. Oil enters into non-drying fats, in terms of quality it is equal to olive oil. The stem, Leaf are good food for livestock and animals. Groundnut accumulates biological nitrogen in the soil, increasing soil fertility. Plowed fields 2-3 times are planted in the spring (at the end of April) when the soil temperature rises to 14-15°. Demanding on phosphorus and nitrogen fertilizers. 70-100 kg of seeds are spent per hectare. During the growing season, it is watered 4-6 times. The row is processed between them, chopped 2-3 times during the growing season, the yield is greatly increased if the root collar is buried with soil. Currently, 4 varieties of groundnut are grown in Uzbekistan. Soybeans (Glycine) is a genus of annual herbaceous plants, legumes and oilseeds, native to cornfields. 10 species Africa and Jan. In the humid tropics and subtropics of East Asia, wild species 1 is found in the Far East. Homeland-China. Soy is a crop that has been cultivated for a very long time. Mil. av. 5ming is planted from the anniversary. It is grown in the United States, RF, India, Japan, Korea, Indonesia, Ukraine, Moldavia, Georgia and Uzbekistan. The world's soybean crop is maize. 73.6 million. ga, average grain yield 22.1 s/ Ha (2000): 20-a in Uzbekistan. of 60y. began to spread widely from their fields.

The root of the common soybean (Glycine max) species is well developed, the axial root, sershox, penetrates into the soil to a depth of 2 m, the main part settles in the expelled layer (at the root the fungal bacteria develop). The STEM is rough, cylindrical, grows erect, but there are also varieties that can lie down. Height from 15 cm to 2 m, branching, with 2-8 lateral branches. The Leaf is serrated, banded, the length of the band is 8-20 CM, the length of the leaflet is 13-15 CM. The flower is small, white or Pink, collected in a dense inflorescence, settles in the leaf axils. The fruit is legumes, yellow, black, brown, hard. Each Duchy has 2-6 grains, 1000 grains weigh 40-425 g. It contains 24-45% protein, 13-37% fat, 20-32% carbohydrates, 1-2% lycin, vitamins D, E and B. Fat, protein and lycin are extracted from the seed. The growing season is 75-200 days. Soy is a hot-loving and moisture-loving, yorug-loving short-day plant. Develops well at 21-23°. The seeds germinate at 8– 10°. The shade is self-pollinated. The flowering period lasts 15-55 days. Soy flour and oil are

obtained from it. Grain, immature (dumbbell) beans are used for food. Soy flour is used in the preparation of milk, cottage cheese, confectionery. Salmon, tuponi, Blue Stem, Silo are fed to livestock as feed. In Uzbekistan Rice Culture in 1981-88, Uzbekistan 2, Uzbekistan 6, Friendship varieties of soybeans were issued and zoned for all regions.

Conclusion the Fergana Valley area is strongly influenced by anthropogenic factors, and the vegetation cover of the area assumes constant study of the species and species composition, recording innovations, changes and, accordingly, developing measures to preserve the composition of rare and endangered species and species. On Earth, representatives of the cornucopia family make up 5%, in Central Asia-14%, in Uzbekistan-9.5%, in the Fergana Valley-4%, which means that it is important to preserve representatives of the cornucopia family.

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